

OPENING ADDRESS

by

George Marx

Thank you for all of you having come back to Balaton! This meeting is a new proof that our field of science is really an exciting one in these days. When preparing this talk I collected the proceedings volumes of the previous Neutrino Conferences, I myself, was astonished by the fast progress in the experimental technique and by the fast change in theoretical ideas.

- I. Moscow /1968/, sponsored by the Academy of USSR
- II. Cortona /1970/, sponsored by the Academia dei Lincei
- III. Balaton /1972/, sponsored by the European Physical Society
- IV. Philadelphia /1974/, sponsored by the AEC and NSF of USA
- V. Balaton /1975/, sponsored by IUPAP and in 1976, may be in Aachen.

The first meeting was organized just after the observation of the cosmic ray neutrino events in the deep gold mines of India, South Africa and Utah. This was the "golden age", when the scientists were happy about each observed energetic neutrino.

Two years later, in Cortona, the puzzle of the Solar Neutrinos came into the focus of public interest.

We met at Lake Balaton in 1972, when the new powerful CERN beam started operating. The higher energy Batavia beam came into sight. From the sky the eyes turned to the laboratories. Bruno Pontecorvo called the "Neutrino 72" meeting to be a conference of inequalities, i.e. a conference of negative results. But Victor Weisskopf, the theoretician spoke about the importance of the Salam Weinberg strategy in understanding the weak interactions and Richard Feynman predicted a fundamental role of

neutrino beams in exploring the structure of hadrons. Weisskopf quoted three events: The discovery of the nucleus in 1911. The discovery of the neutron in 1932. The discovery of the first baryon resonance in 1952. In each 20 years something new started. "The year 1972 may be the beginning of a new era in physics", said Weisskopf. That Balaton meeting was a conference of great hopes.

The hopes were justified. At the Neutrino 1974, the last year oversea, the firm existence of neutral currents had been reported. The Salam Weinberg approach turned out to be fruitful one. The scaling observed at CERN and in Batavia justified Feynman's prediction: the neutrino beams penetrated the deep structure of the proton.

And then there came the "gipsy time", the first indications for new sorts of matter. These experiments are the highlights of our conference, concentrating the attention of field theoreticians and quark phenomenologists upon the same problem. New forces, new structures, new particles have been discovered, not to make the life of physicists harder, as in the former decade, but to make our picture of matter more elegant. Not only hopes, but considerable progress is going to be reported. The expected new era of fundamental science has arrived. In this new period the elusive neutrinos are going to play so important role, as the good old electrons.

I have to ask you to forgive us all the mistakes we committed in the organization. We try to offer an up to date program, by the International Organizing Committee, which has created this meeting.

The two lime trees planted by Richard Feynman and Bruno Pontecorvo at the lake shore 3 years ago have grown higher. So did the neutrino science, too. So, let us turn to our job, let us see the recent progress in details.